

РЕГІОНАЛЬНІ ДИСПРОПОРЦІЇ ТА СОЦІАЛЬНЕ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНІ

Набієва Г. І.

Останніми роками Азербайджан демонструє значне економічне зростання, що відображається у зростанні ВВП та макроекономічних показників. Однак розподіл економічних вигод між регіонами та соціальними групами залишається нерівномірним. У цьому дослідженні розглядається вплив економічного зростання на соціальний добробут із акцентом на регіональних відмінностях у доходах на душу населення та заробітній платі працівників. Використовуючи Індекс людського розвитку, Індекс якості життя та пов'язані з ними субіндекси, аналіз висвітлює стійку нерівність доходів і її наслідки для інклюзивного розвитку. Запропоновано рекомендації щодо державної політики для забезпечення справедливого розподілу економічних здобутків, підтримки регіонального розвитку та підвищення матеріального добробуту вразливих груп населення.

Ключові слова: *економічне зростання, соціальний добробут, регіональна нерівність доходів, Індекс якості життя, матеріальний добробут, інклюзивний розвиток.*

Introduction. In recent years, Azerbaijan has experienced notable economic growth, with increases observed in GDP and other macroeconomic indicators. In order to assess the impact of this growth on the social welfare of the population, the Human Development Index (HDI), its key components (education, healthcare, and income indicators), the poverty rate, and several additional indicators have been adopted as primary criteria. The results of the study indicate that the acceleration of economic growth has made a significant contribution to improving social welfare. However, the effects of this growth have not been equally distributed across all segments of society[1].

One of the key issues in evaluating the impact of economic development on

social welfare is not only the increase in GDP, but also the reduction of poverty and the improvement of living standards among low-income populations. The benefits of economic growth should be distributed more equitably across all segments of society, particularly among the most vulnerable groups.

The government's socially oriented policies, particularly the increase in budget expenditures on education and healthcare, have had a somewhat positive impact on improving the living standards of the population. Progress achieved in the education sector has contributed to enhancing workforce skills, vocational training, and the development of human capital. In the healthcare sector, increased investments have led to improvements in public health indicators, longer life expectancy, and reduced disease risks. Nevertheless, these improvements have not been sufficient to ensure an equitable distribution of social welfare. Regional income disparities, as well as differences in the quality and accessibility of social services, remain key factors hindering inclusiveness.

Preliminary analysis has shown that when the social outcomes of economic growth are assessed solely within the framework of macroeconomic indicators, income inequality across different population groups is not fully captured. Therefore, in order to ensure the sustainable development of social welfare, not only the magnitude of economic growth but also its fair and inclusive distribution should be considered as a key criterion. The existing level of income inequality has a significant impact on ensuring social justice among different population groups.

The main objective of this study is to develop recommendations aimed at strengthening the relationship between social welfare and economic development. Particular attention is given to examining the interrelationship between income inequality and social welfare in greater depth. This approach allows for the consideration not only of the nominal indicators of social welfare but also of its qualitative and equity dimensions.

The conducted analyses demonstrate that the impact of economic growth on social welfare indicators depends not only on macroeconomic variables but is also closely related to income distribution, regional income disparities, and the quality of

social services. In this regard, ensuring the inclusiveness of social welfare requires the implementation of social programs aimed at reducing regional disparities and improving both the quality and accessibility of social services.

One of the most important approaches to assessing social welfare is the analysis of quality of life indicators. The “Quality of Life in Azerbaijan” index is a composite indicator reflecting the population’s standard of living, social protection, and overall welfare level. This index considers not only income levels but also factors such as education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and social equality. Evaluating quality of life from a regional perspective in Azerbaijan allows for the identification of unequal distribution of social welfare.

The Quality of Life Index has been compiled and published biennially in Azerbaijan since 2018. This index enables the monitoring of changes in the socio-economic conditions of the population as well as regional inequalities. It covers 11 economic regions of Azerbaijan, including 6 cities of republican subordination and 61 administrative districts. The final indicator of the ranking, the Quality of Life Index (QLI), is calculated as the weighted average of 7 sub-indices. The QLI, its sub-indices, and the underlying indicators are normalized to a range of [1, 5] using the formula $4 \times [(V_i - V_{\min}) / (V_{\max} - V_{\min})] + 1$. A value of “5” indicates the best performance in terms of quality of life and its components compared to other regions (cities and districts), while “1” represents the lowest performance [2].

Although the structure of the Quality of Life Index consists of several sub-indices, the material well-being sub-index carries the highest weight and, according to expert opinion, serves as the principal component in determining the level of social welfare. Material well-being encompasses indicators reflecting income opportunities, living conditions, and property ownership. This sub-index is calculated as the weighted average of five indexed indicators (sub-components): average annual nominal income per capita, average monthly nominal wages of employees, the average amount of assigned monthly pensions, total housing area per capita, and the number of passenger cars. Since these indicators directly reflect the material conditions and economic welfare of the population, they are considered among the

most influential components in determining the overall index value.

Table 1 – Quality of Life Index Indicators (2018-2022)

	Per Capita Nominal Income (Index)			Average Monthly Nominal Wage of Employees (Index)		
	2018	2020	2022	2018	2020	2022
Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic	1,65	1,66	1,67	1,88	2,18	2,40
Absheron-Khizi economic region	1,57	1,35	1,68	1,80	2,32	2,63
Daghlig Shirvan economic region	1,41	1,44	1,54	1,52	1,97	2,24
Ganja-Dashkasan economic region	1,62	1,65	1,82	1,64	2,10	2,40
Gazakh-Tovuz economic region	1,41	1,45	1,59	1,53	2,01	2,31
Guba-Khachmaz economic region	1,46	1,52	1,64	1,59	2,08	2,31
Lankaran-Astara economic region	1,34	1,35	1,46	1,51	1,93	2,21
Central Aran economic region	1,61	1,64	1,76	1,45	1,90	2,15
Mil-Mughan economic region	1,31	1,34	1,46	1,46	1,91	2,15
Shaki-Zagatala economic region	1,39	1,42	1,52	1,46	1,88	2,12
Shirvan-Salyan economic region	1,52	1,58	1,72	1,69	2,13	2,45

Source: <https://economics.org.az/az/announcements/9748>

Table 1 presents the sub-index values of the first two indicators across economic regions for the years 2018, 2020, and 2022.

The average annual nominal income per capita (AIC, in manats) is calculated as the sum of income derived from wages, pensions, scholarships, dividends, and the sale of household products.

The average monthly nominal wage of employees (AMNW, in manats) is calculated by dividing the total amount of the accrued monthly wage fund (including taxes and other social contributions) by the number of employees who actually worked.

Graph 1. Per Capita Nominal Income, in Manats (by Economic Regions, 2018–2022) (Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>)

Among the indicators included in the material well-being sub-index, the average annual nominal income per capita and the average monthly nominal wage of employees are of particular importance for assessing regional income inequality.

A comparison of statistical data for 2018 and 2022 indicates that nominal per capita incomes across regions were characterized by significant disparities. In 2018, the minimum observed value was 1,578.5 manats, while the maximum reached 6,119.9 manats. The gap between the minimum and maximum values for that year amounted to 4,541.4 manats.

In 2020, this gap decreased to some extent, with the minimum value recorded at 1,459.8 manats and the maximum at 4,896.7 manats. Thus, the difference between the two extremes was 3,436.9 manats. Although this reflects a partial reduction in disparity, it also indicates that income inequality had not been fully eliminated.

During the period 2018–2020, although nominal per capita incomes generally increased in absolute terms, regional income disparities persisted. The relative narrowing of the gap can be associated with a partial increase in economic activity in certain regions; however, the unequal distribution of socio-economic opportunities continued to sustain income inequality.

According to statistical data for 2022, the minimum per capita income was recorded in Yardimli district at 1,719.1 manats, while the maximum was observed in the city of Naftalan at 7,344.4 manats.

The difference between these two values amounted to 5,625.3 manats, indicating a substantial disparity in income levels across the country's regions. Such a gap can be explained not only by the unequal distribution of economic activity and employment opportunities but also by differences in the socio-economic potential of regions. In tourism-oriented areas such as Naftalan, higher revenues generated from the service sector have a positive impact on income levels. In contrast, in agriculture-oriented and less industrialized regions—particularly mountainous districts such as Yardimli—income levels remain relatively low due to limited economic activities and lower levels of investment [3].

In 2022, compared to previous years, a renewed increase in income inequality was observed.

One of the key indicators for assessing regional income inequality is the average monthly nominal wage of employees. This indicator represents one of the primary sources of income for the population (see Graph 2).

Graph 2. Average Monthly Nominal Wage of Employees, in Manats (by Economic Regions, 2018–2024) (Source: <https://www.stat.gov.az/>)

In 2018, the minimum observed value of the average monthly nominal wage of employees was 259.2 manats, while the maximum reached 499.4 manats. The difference between the minimum and maximum values for that year amounted to 240.2 manats.

In 2020, these figures increased, with the minimum wage rising to 393.9 manats and the maximum to 650.4 manats. Consequently, the gap between the two extremes was 256.5 manats.

In 2022, a more pronounced increase in the average monthly nominal wage of employees was recorded, with the minimum value observed in Qakh district at 451.3 manats and the maximum in Dashkasan district at 956.4 manats. As a result, the interregional gap widened to 505.1 manats, indicating a significant rise in inequality compared to previous years.

By 2024, the actual minimum value was 538.4 manats (still in Qakh district),

while the maximum reached 1,145.5 manats in Dashkasan district. The difference between these values, 607.1 manats, represents a historically high level of regional income inequality. This demonstrates that disparities in wages across regions are increasing at an accelerating pace.

The high average wages in Dashkasan district are primarily attributable to the presence of industrial and mining activities, as well as the employment of workers in highly specialized fields. This leads to higher wage levels compared to other regions. In contrast, the low minimum observed in Qakh district can be explained by the predominance of agricultural and small business activities, the relatively underdeveloped industrial and service sectors, and limited investment opportunities. These factors contribute to lower average wages in the region. Wage disparities are largely determined by the economic structure of regions, the share of industrial and service sectors, and the unequal distribution of investment and employment opportunities.

Although per capita nominal incomes and average nominal wages of employees have increased over the years, disparities across regions remain high. This underscores the persistence of regional income inequality in Azerbaijan and the uneven distribution of social welfare across the country. Nominal growth alone is insufficient; the primary objective should be equitable and inclusive growth. Ensuring that economic development benefits all districts equally is crucial for the sustainable improvement of social welfare.

To reduce regional income inequality, investments in industry, tourism, and service sectors should be distributed evenly across regions. Additionally, support should be provided for the development of agriculture and local businesses, thereby increasing employment opportunities and enhancing material welfare. The existence of interregional disparities indicates that government social protection and economic support policies must be targeted. In other words, underdeveloped regions should receive special attention, and resources should be optimized to enhance their social welfare.

Azerbaijan possesses all necessary resources—both financial-material and

intellectual—to align increases in material welfare with socio-cultural development. Achieving this strategic objective requires the formulation and implementation of a comprehensive, long-term socio-economic policy in which all components are fully integrated and mutually reinforcing.

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted analysis has shown that in recent years various reforms have been implemented in Azerbaijan aimed at developing the economy, improving social welfare, and ensuring social security at the same time. As a result, growth has been observed in the indicators characterizing economic development and social welfare.

However, there are certain discrepancies between the level of economic development and social development in the country. Consequently, regional disparities still persist. Although significant results have been achieved in reducing poverty, income levels in rural areas remain lower compared to urban areas. Income inequality exists, and the development of the non-oil sector is weak.

At the present stage, one of the priorities of the country's social policy should be the reduction of income inequality. This would also mean ensuring social security in the country.

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REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND SOCIAL WELFARE IN AZERBAIJAN

Nabiyeva G. I.

In recent years, Azerbaijan has experienced significant economic growth, reflected in rising GDP and macroeconomic indicators. However, the distribution of economic benefits across regions and social groups remains unequal. This study examines the impact of economic growth on social welfare, focusing on regional disparities in per capita income and employee wages. Using the Human Development

Index, Quality of Life Index, and related sub-indices, the analysis highlights persistent income inequality and its implications for inclusive development. Policy recommendations are proposed to ensure equitable distribution of economic gains, support regional development, and enhance the material well-being of vulnerable populations.

Keywords: *economic growth, social welfare, regional income inequality, Quality of Life Index, material well-being, inclusive development.*